

Islamist charters as *tafsīr* texts:
The Hamas covenant as modern exegesis

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Introduction

When approaching Islamist charters we mainly read it as political activist texts using Islamic discourse. For charters as that of Hamas, political activism is also clearly the main motivation and context wherein it developed.¹ I want to propose in this paper that Islamic source-texts aren't simply cited as a means to authorize the political program and place the political objectives within a religio-cosmological scheme, the texts aren't simply used, the usage also implies a proposed exegesis. Islamists charters can thus also be seen as belonging to the exegesis tradition of the Qur'ān (*tafsīr*) and Ḥadīth (*sharḥ*).² The way they use certain source-texts isn't classical and sometimes even doubtful according to classical scientific norms of *tafsīr* and *sharḥ*, as to claim the truthfulness of one's political stance through source-texts is generally frowned upon.³ This is also explained by the fact that many Islamist leadership, as that of the Muslim Brotherhood and that of Hamas, are not formally trained in the Islamic sciences.⁴ But even though they use source-texts in non-classical ways, for them their political or societal claim is connected or supported by the source-texts they cite with it. I will use the Hamas charter⁵ to test this thesis as 21 of the 36 articles of the covenant uses Qur'ān verses or

¹ Are Knudsen, 'Crescent and Sword: The Hamas Enigma', *Third World Quarterly* 26, no. 8 (1 January 2005): 1377 – 1379.

² For example, see the Syrian Muslim Brotherhood charter: http://www.memri.org/report/en/print6250.htm#_ednref1 (English), <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/arabic/2012/3/26/%D9%88%D8%AB%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%A9-%D8%B9%D9%87%D8%AF-%D9%88%D9%85%D9%8A%D8%AB%D8%A7%D9%82-%D8%A5%D8%AE%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%86-%D8%B3%D9%88%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A7> (Arabic). And the charter of the Moroccan al-Iṣlāḥ movement: <http://alislah.ma/images/stories/mitak.pdf>. All accessed on 9 June 2015.

³ Hussein Abdul-Raof, *Theological Approaches to Qur'anic Exegesis: A Practical Comparative-Contrastive Analysis* (United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis, 2012), 1-8.

⁴ Knudsen, *ibid*, 1377.

⁵ I use the English translation available at the Yale website: 'The Avalon Project: Hamas Covenant 1988', accessed 28 March 2015, http://avalon.law.yale.edu/20th_century/hamas.asp, for the Arabic version see: <http://www.aljazeera.net/specialfiles/pages/0b4f24e4-7c14-4f50-a831-ea2b6e73217d>, accessed 9 June 2015

Ḥadīth traditions, which provides enough material to review their proposed exegesis on some key verses. How much can Islamists charters as that of Hamas be seen as belonging to the classical exegesis tradition, and how orthodox or heterodox are their proposed meanings and applications of these sourcetexts? Especially this last question is relevant to see if orthodox Sunni Islam is a viable ground for Islamist visions of Islam and the world.

According to Hussein Abdul-Raof this thematic usage of Qur'ānic texts, as seen in the Hamas covenant, makes it fall under three typologies of exegesis in order of hierarchy:

- 1) Rational exegesis (*Tafsīr bi-IRā'y*)
- 2) Literary style exegesis
- 3) Thematic (*mawḍū'ī*) non-sequenced exegesis (*ghayri musalsal*)⁶

As the exegesis is used without referring to Prophetic commentary or that of the first generations of Muslims (who are the *Salaf al-ṣāliḥ*, the righteous predecessors), it falls under rational non-traditional exegesis, even if they deem their understanding and application of the Qur'ānic text as traditional.⁷ Abdul-Raof defines this type of exegesis as "a rational technique adopted to achieve socio-educational reform" and "aims to raise political awareness and calls for political reform", which he labels "socio-political exegesis".⁸ The exegesis he mentions as typifying this form of exegesis is Sayyid Quṭb (d. 1966)'s *Fī zilāl al-Qur'ān*, who was one of the ideologues of the Egyptian Muslim Brotherhood, and who's works were an important

⁶ Abdul-Raof, *ibid*, 3-4, 29-31.

⁷ As is claimed in article 5 of the Hamas charter.

⁸ Abdul-Raof, *ibid*, 57-58.

inspiration for the founders of Hamas⁹, whereby we can even claim that the Hamas charter is a summary of Quṭb's thought¹⁰, which we will discuss further in our analysis below.

Comparative analysis between classical and Islamist exegesis

The exegesis of several verses proposed in the Hamas covenant will be compared to the exegesis of Sayyid Quṭb¹¹, who, as mentioned, was their main inspiration, and to the 13th century scholar al-Bayḍāwī (d. 1286)¹², which, as I have argued elsewhere, can be deemed as normative-representative of the classical Sunnī exegesis tradition, and also belongs to the rational exegesis (*Tafsīr bi-IRā'y*) style.¹³ We will discuss articles from the Hamas charter which doesn't just mention verses, but also clearly provide a proposed meaning to those verses whereby the article becomes the exegesis on the verse itself. Quṭb's socio-political exegesis "laid considerable stress on the need for people to approach the faith intuitively, directly, in a way which need not, indeed could not, be rationalized or explained with reference to any known canon of philosophical criteria. [...] there was an obligation to carry this knowledge of the faith, through direct action, into the life, not simply of the individual,

⁹ Beverly Milton-Edwards and Stephen Farrell, *Hamas* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2010), 39-41.

¹⁰ Bassam Tibi, *From Sayyid Quṭb to Hamas: The Middle East Conflict and the Islamization of Antisemitism* (Working Paper Series, The Yale Initiative for the Interdisciplinary Study of Antisemitism), 10-11, 16-19.

¹¹ Sayyid Quṭb, *Fī zilāl al-Qur'ān* (Cairo: Dār al-Shurūq, 1412 AH) in six volumes. English translation: Sayyid Quṭb, *In the Shade of the Qur'ān*, trans. Adil Salahi (UK: The Islamic Foundation, 2002), in 18 volumes.

¹² 'Abd Allāh al-Bayḍāwī, *Anwār al-Tanzīl wa āsrār al-Tā'wīl*, ed. Maḥmūd 'Abd al-Qādir al-Arnā'wūt (Beirut: Dār Ṣādr, 2004), in two volumes.

¹³ Arnold Yasin Mol, *Modern and Classical Scientific Readings of the Qur'ān A comparative study of Abdul Wadud (d. 2001) and al-Bayḍāwī (d. 1286)'s naturalistic exegesis* (unpublished paper), 5-7.

but also of the social and political order.¹⁴ This ideological vision is mixed with references to Prophetic commentary and classical opinions, but the vision remains dominant. Classical exegesis works as that of al-Bayḍāwī discuss multiple aspects of a verse such as its linguistics, historical context, its relation to other verses or Prophetic commentary, and its theological, legal or ethical meaning as understood by the exegete's school of thought. I will mention some of these elements to show the similarities or contrasts with that of Hamas' application. For an extensive analysis we would need more exegetical works from different time periods, but as this paper is only a proposal we focus only on these three works. I have added them in a side by side overview as an appendix.

In article 3 Hamas (H) links verse 21:18 with the struggle of *Jihād*, while both al-Bayḍāwī (B) and Quṭb (Q) read it together with the preceding verses about God's creative act, but the latter also places the concept of truth in a cosmological system wherein falsehood cannot truly exist. In article 9 (H) links its resistance movement so the Islamic state can be established and justice restored. For (B) the verse is general in that God helps the Muslims against the unbelievers so the latter's spreading of corruption can be stopped. (Q) on the other hand sees this strife as part of God's scheme towards progress and goodness. It isn't only violent strife, but also competitiveness on all fields which nurture people's talents, a clear reference to the 19th century popular idea of Social Darwinism. In article 12 (H) presents nationalism as being part of the Islamic creed, a very heavy statement as Islamists as (Q) were vehemently opposed to any nationalism which would divide the Muslim community and saw as *Jahiliyya*, pre-Islamic paganism.¹⁵ (H) claims nationalism through the famous **{There is no compulsion in**

¹⁴ Charles Tripp, 'Sayyid Qutb: The Political Vision', in *Pioneers of Islamic Revival (Studies in Islamic Society)*, ed. Ali Rahnama (Malaysia: Zed Books, 2005), 161.

¹⁵ Tripp, *Ibid*, 162-164.

religion} verse (2:256), but of which they only cite the latter part which says that one should denounce *al-Ṭāghūt*, in modern Islamist exegesis as that of (Q) understood as referring to manmade (i.e. non-Islamic and secular) laws, and the belief in God and hold fast to **{the firmest handle (*al-Wuthqā*) for which there is no breaking}**, again a clear reference to Islamist discourse as *al-Wuthqā* was used for the Pan-Islamic movement.¹⁶ For (H) this verse makes resistance an individual duty on every Muslim, whereby nobody needs any political, scholarly or family permission to go out and fight.¹⁷ Article 13 uses verse 2:120 **{Never will the Jews and Christians be pleased with you unless you follow their creed}**, as a way to show God warns Muslims that you can't trust non-Muslims in making fair treaties, while classical Islam does accept non-Muslims ambassadors as arbitrators to come to a treaty.¹⁸ This explanation by (H) is clearly taken from (Q) who sees this as a constant struggle by Zionism, Christian Imperialism, and Communism against Islam, and that there can be no negotiations or compromises. For (B), the verse just says that some groups will not follow the Prophet and that he should focus on what is revealed to him instead of trying to please these groups. Article 32 refers to verses 8:16 and 5:64 which (H) sees as a call to never leave the struggle against Zionism which it heads. For (B) the first verse is about war tactics during the historical battle of Badr (624 CE), and the latter verse about how every time the Jews created corruption God placed another political authority over them, from Nebuchadnezzar to the Persians to the Muslims. For (Q) the first verse is also about war tactics but has ahistorical meaning for Muslims to never give up as as true believers they know death is predetermined

¹⁶ Umar Ryad, *Islamic Reformism and Christianity: A Critical Reading of the Works of Muhammad Rashid Rida and His Associates (1898-1935)* (United States: Brill, 2009), 3.

¹⁷ For the implications on this, see: Ahmed al-Dawoody, *The Islamic Law of War: Justifications and Regulations* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011), 76.

¹⁸ To have peace treaties with non-Muslim nations was the normal state of affairs for Muslim states in classical Islam, see: Ahmed al-Dawoody, *Ibid*, 93-102.

and that they trust in God's help in battle or reward for martyrdom. The latter verse is understood as referring to the inner strife between Jews, and if Muslims return to Islam and unite as a community, the Jews will try to stop this.

Conclusion

When looking at Islamists charters as that of Hamas, I propose that we can look at them as a form of modern exegesis. In our short comparative analysis we have seen that the Hamas charter provides a proposed meaning of the verses. In this, they were certainly influenced by Sayyid Quṭb, but they also provided new meanings that serve their own project such as seeing nationalism as part of the Islamic creed. The Hamas charter provides very specific exegetical meanings linked to their struggle whereby both the Qur'ānic text and the struggle for Islamic unity is made universal and ahistorical, but at the same time directly contextual to their struggle. When compared to classical exegesis it is clear their approaches differ immensely, as did their contexts. It will be interesting to see if further analysis of other Islamist charters show similar heterodox forms of exegesis. Our current analysis already shows how contemporary Muslims simultaneously provide but also obtain meaning from the Qur'ān, which they clearly view as a living text which supports and give meaning to their political struggle.

Bibliography:

Abdul-Raof, Hussein. *Theological Approaches to Qur'anic Exegesis: A Practical Comparative-Contrastive Analysis*. Abingdon: Routledge, 2012.

al-Bayḍāwī, 'Abd Allāh. *Anwār Al-Tanzīl Wa Āsrār Al-Tā'wīl*. Edited by Maḥmūd 'Abd al-Qādir al-Arnā'wūṭ. 2nd ed. Beirut: Dār Ṣādr, 2004.

al-Dawoody, Ahmed. *The Islamic Law of War: Justifications and Regulations*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011.

Knudsen, Are. 'Crescent and Sword: The Hamas Enigma', *Third World Quarterly* 26, no. 8 (1 January 2005): 1373 – 1388.

Milton-Edwards, Beverly, and Stephen Farrell. *Hamas*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2010.

Mol, Arnold Yasin. *Modern and Classical Scientific Readings of the Qur'ān A comparative study of Abdul Wadud (d. 2001) and al-Bayḍāwī (d. 1286)'s naturalistic exegesis* (unpublished paper), 5-7. Available at: [https://www.academia.edu/12867581/](https://www.academia.edu/12867581/Modern_and_Classical_Scientific_Readings_of_the_Qur)

Modern and Classical Scientific Readings of the Qur
%C4%81n A comparative study of Abdul Wadud d. 2001 and al-Bay%E1%B8%8D
%C4%81w%C4%AB_d. 1286 s naturalistic exegesis

Quṭb, Sayyid. *Fī zilāl al-Qur'ān*. Cairo: Dār al-Shurūq, 1412 AH.

Quṭb, Sayyid. *In the Shade of the Qur'ān*. Translated by Adil Salahi. UK: The Islamic Foundation, 2002.

Ryad, Umar. *Islamic Reformism and Christianity: A Critical Reading of the Works of Muhammad Rashid Rida and His Associates (1898-1935)*. United States: Brill, 2009.

Tibi, Bassam. *From Sayyid Qutb to Hamas: The Middle East Conflict and the Islamization of Antisemitism*. Working Paper Series, The Yale Initiative for the Interdisciplinary Study of Antisemitism, accessed 9 June 2015, <http://www.isgap.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/10/bassam-tibi-online-working-paper-20101.pdf>

Tripp, Charles. 'Sayyid Qutb: The Political Vision'. In *Pioneers of Islamic Revival (Studies in Islamic Society)*, ed. Ali Rahnama. Malaysia: Zed Books, 2005.

Charters:

al-Iṣlāḥ movement (Morocco): 'Mīthāq Ḥarakah al-Tawḥīd wa al-'iṣlāḥ', accessed 9 June 2015, <http://alislah.ma/images/stories/mitak.pdf>

Hamas charter:

English translation: ‘*The Avalon Project: Hamas Covenant 1988*’, accessed 28 March 2015, http://avalon.law.yale.edu/20th_century/hamas.asp.

Arabic original: ‘*Mīthāq Ḥarakah al-Muqāwwamah al-ʿislamiyyah (Hamās)*’, accessed 9 June 2015, <http://www.aljazeera.net/specialfiles/pages/0b4f24e4-7c14-4f50-a831-ea2b6e73217d>

Syrian Muslim Brotherhood charter:

English translation: ‘*Syrian Muslim Brotherhood: We will establish a Democratic, Civil, Egalitarian State once Assad is ousted*’, accessed 9 June 2015, http://www.memri.org/report/en/print6250.htm#_ednref1.

Arabic original: ‘*Ahd wa Mīthāq*’, accessed 9 June 2015, <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/arabic/2012/3/26/%D9%88%D8%AB%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%A9-%D8%B9%D9%87%D8%AF-%D9%88%D9%85%D9%8A%D8%AB%D8%A7%D9%82-%D8%A5%D8%AE%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%86-%D8%B3%D9%88%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A7>.

Appendix: Side by side overview of the three exegetical works¹⁹

<p>Qur'ān 21:18</p>	<p>"We bring forward the Truth to crush and destroy falsehood; it is doomed to be banished. Woe to you for your way of thinking about God."</p>
<p>Hamas:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "[The Muslims in the IRM] fear Allah and raise the banner of Jihad in the face of the oppressors, so that they would rid the land and the people of their uncleanness, vileness and evils." [Art.3]
<p>al-Bayḍāwī:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Striking a similitude on entertainment and that (God) is too transcendent in His essence for any entertaining games." [2:663, he reads it together with the previous verses 21:16-17 as one whole]
<p>Quṭb:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "It is all a theoretical argument given here in order to establish the basic truth that whatever relates to God is, like Him, ever-present and eternal. Hence, if God wants to enjoy some pastime, such pastime would not relate to anything that is created such as the heavens, the earth or anything in between. All these are new, in the sense that they are created at a certain point in time. What relates to God remains with Him, eternally, so as to fit in with His Majesty. But the law that operates for all time is that there is no such thing as a pastime in respect of God. There are only seriousness and truth. [...] Those who believe in God entertain no doubt that His promise will come true, or that the truth enjoys prime position in the structure of the universe and its system. They are also certain that victory will eventually belong to the truth. Hence, if God tests them by allowing falsehood a temporary triumph, they realize that this is merely a test God puts them through so as to eradicate their weakness or give them what they lack. He wants them to be fit to receive the victorious truth, and to make them the tool by which He accomplishes His purpose. Thus, He lets them go through the test, to equip them properly for their role. If they hasten to remedy their weakness and redress their drawbacks, God will shorten their period of test and accomplish through them whatever He wishes. The ultimate result is a foregone conclusion: "We hurl the truth against falsehood, and it crushes the latter, and behold, it withers away." (Verse 18) God accomplishes what He wills." [12:16-17]
<p>Qur'ān 2:251</p>	<p>"...Had God not made one group of people repel the other, the earth would have become full of corruption (<i>li-fasadati al-'arḍ</i>), but God is generous to His creatures."</p>

¹⁹ To avoid excessive footnotes, the article in the Hamas charter, and the volume and page number of al-Bayḍāwī's and Quṭb's exegesis will be mentioned in brackets. I will also abbreviate "Islamic Resistance Movement" with IRM, and edit out parts that mention unnecessary details or is repetitive, this is indicated by [...]. All Qur'ān translations are by Muhammad Sarwar (1982 edition), with adaptations such as added transliteration or when the translation deviates too much from the original Arabic. I use the English translations of the Hamas charter and of Quṭb's exegesis, and al-Bayḍāwī is translated into English by the author.

Qur'ān 21:18	"We bring forward the Truth to crush and destroy falsehood; it is doomed to be banished. Woe to you for your way of thinking about God."
Hamās:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "The IRM found itself at a time when Islam has disappeared from life. Thus rules shook, concepts were upset, values changed and evil people took control, oppression and darkness prevailed, cowards became like tigers: homelands were usurped, people were scattered and were caused to wander all over the world, the state of justice disappeared and the state of falsehood replaced it. Nothing remained in its right place. Thus, when Islam is absent from the arena, everything changes. From this state of affairs the incentives are drawn. As for the objectives: They are the fighting against the false, defeating it and vanquishing it so that justice could prevail, homelands be retrieved and from its mosques would the voice of the mu'azen emerge declaring the establishment of the state of Islam, so that people and things would return each to their right places and Allah is our helper." [Art.9]
al-Baydāwī:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "And if He, He be praised and exalted, did not push some people against some others and He helps the Muslims against the unbelievers and He refrains through them (i.e. the Muslims) their corruption, [...] or corrupting the earth with their evil. And it can be read as 'beneficial' (<i>nāfa'a</i>, instead of <i>dāfa'a</i>, push)." [1:138]
Quṭb:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "This powerful statement takes us beyond the limited narrative and its personalities and events to reveal the fundamental divine wisdom underlying the constant contention, power struggles and battles among the multitudes of mankind in the tumult of life. It depicts the incessant strife and the spirit of competition and rivalry that drive human beings to their various ends and objectives in this world, according to the overall divine scheme under God's wise hand which leads them all towards progress and higher standards of life. Were it not for this spirit of struggle and competition, life would be dull and stale. The conflict of interests and the variety of objectives that people seek in this world are the means by which human talent and energy are released and brought into play to reinvigorate and revitalize the human experience for the good of mankind. This dynamic movement produces the true human force of goodness, brings truth to the fore, enhances man's sense of right and wrong, and firmly establishes justice on earth. It enables true and sincere believers to identify their noble role in life. It provides them with the will and strength to persevere and fulfil that role in total obedience to God's order and tireless pursuit of His pleasure and blessings. God then intervenes on the side of the believers so that the truth they are upholding will prevail. Human conflict becomes a positive and constructive struggle for the good of mankind and a better life in this world. The fact that the smaller group of believers have placed their trust in God, and are devoted to fulfilling His ultimate will in protecting life and establishing the truth and defending it, enables them to eventually triumph and prevail." [1:330-331]

Qur'ān 2:256	"...Whoever rejects the devil (<i>al-Ṭāghūt</i>) and believes in God and has firmly taken hold of a strong handle that never breaks. God is All-hearing and knowing."
Hamās:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Nationalism, from the point of view of the IRM, is part of the religious creed. Nothing in nationalism is more significant or deeper than in the case when an enemy should tread Moslem land. Resisting and quelling the enemy become the individual duty of every Moslem, male or female. A woman can go out to fight the enemy without her husband's permission, and so does the slave: without his master's permission. Nothing of the sort is to be found in any other regime. This is an undisputed fact. If other nationalist movements are connected with materialistic, human or regional causes, nationalism of the IRM has all these elements as well as the more important elements that give it soul and life. It is connected to the source of spirit and the granter of life, hoisting in the sky of the homeland the heavenly banner that joins earth and heaven with a strong bond. If Moses comes and throws his staff, both witch and magic are annulled." [Art.12]
al-Bayḍāwī:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "{And whoever rejects <i>al-Ṭāghūt</i>} Satan, or idol statues, or everything that is worshipped other than God, or (rejecting) what deters from worshipping God the most high. And so you be elevated from tyranny (<i>al-Ṭāghiyān</i>) you had overthrown assigned by Him and for His community. {And believes in God} in monotheism and belief in the Messenger. "{And has firmly taken hold of a strong handle} He seeks the seizure of himself with the strong handle from strong cord, and is borrowed from taking hold of the truth from correct insight and proper rational opinion (<i>al-Rā'y</i>). {that does not break} it doesn't discontinue." [1:140]
Quṭb:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "It is false deities that must be rejected, while faith must be reserved for God, who alone deserves faith and trust. The Arabic term for 'false deities' is ṭāghūt, meaning tyranny, a word denoting anything or anyone that takes hold of the mind or suppresses the truth, or transgresses the laws and limits set by God. It refers to forces and systems that disregard the divine religious, moral, social and legal order and operate in this life on values and principles not sanctioned by God or derived from His guidance and teachings. To resist such forces, in all their manifestations, and to believe in God's oneness is the only certain path to success and salvation. The sūrah presents us, yet again, with another vivid image to express an abstract truth. Faith in God provides the believer with a strong and unshakeable support that guarantees him certain liberation. In its essence, faith is a recognition of the most fundamental truth, the existence of God, upon which all reality stands, and acknowledgement of the laws God has laid down for the world and by which the world exists and operates. Believers who hold to God's Guidance are assured of never drifting away from God's path or losing their way." [1:349-350]

<p>Qur'ān 2:120</p>	<p>"The Jews and Christians will never be pleased with you unless you follow their creed. (Muhammad) say to them that the guidance of God is the only true guidance. If you follow their desires after all the knowledge that has come to you, you will no longer have God as your guardian and helper."</p>
<p>Hamas:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Initiatives, and so-called peaceful solutions and international conferences, are in contradiction to the principles of the IRM. Abusing any part of Palestine is abuse directed against part of religion. Nationalism of the IRM is part of its religion. Its members have been fed on that. For the sake of hoisting the banner of Allah over their homeland they fight. "Allah will be prominent, but most people do not know." Now and then the call goes out for the convening of an international conference to look for ways of solving the (Palestinian) question. Some accept, others reject the idea, for this or other reason, with one stipulation or more for consent to convening the conference and participating in it. Knowing the parties constituting the conference, their past and present attitudes towards Moslem problems, the IRM does not consider these conferences capable of realising the demands, restoring the rights or doing justice to the oppressed. These conferences are only ways of setting the infidels in the land of the Moslems as arbitraters. When did the infidels do justice to the believers?" [Art.13]
<p>al-Bayḍāwī:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "{The Jews and Christians will never be pleased with you unless you follow their creed} is an exaggeration in the despair of the Messenger from their Islam, thus that they when they are not pleased with him until he follows their creed, thus how could they follow his faith. And perhaps they said something similar which God related about them and for that He says: {say} teaching him a response. {that the guidance from God is the guidance} meaning God's guidance which is Islam which is the guidance towards the truth [...] {If you follow their desires} their fake opinions. And the creed which God legislated on His servant on the tongue of His prophet, [...] And the desire: an opinion that follows desire {after all the knowledge that has come to you} meaning the revelation, or the known religion which is correct. {you will no longer have God as your guardian and helper} He pushes His punishment on you and He answers truly." [1:90]

<p>Qur'ān 2:120</p>	<p>"The Jews and Christians will never be pleased with you unless you follow their creed. (Muhammad) say to them that the guidance of God is the only true guidance. If you follow their desires after all the knowledge that has come to you, you will no longer have God as your guardian and helper."</p>
<p>Qurṭb:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "This is the bone of contention. What they are after is not evidence or conviction of the truth of Islam. Islam and Muhammad have been a constant obsession with Jews and Christians throughout history. The faith of Islam has always been at the centre of the crusades and campaigns launched against the Muslim community all over the world. No matter how much the two camps may differ or quarrel between themselves, or how divided each of them may be, when it comes to fighting Islam and Muslims they are in full agreement and as united as they could be. The conflict between the Judaeo-Christian world on the one side, and the Muslim community on the other, remains in essence one of ideology, although over the years it has appeared in various guises and has grown more sophisticated and, at times, more insidious. We have seen the original ideological conflict succeeded by economic, political and military confrontation, on the basis that 'religious' or 'ideological' conflicts are outdated and are usually prosecuted by 'fanatics' and backward people. Unfortunately, some naïve and confused Muslims have fallen for this stratagem and persuaded themselves that the religious and ideological aspects of the conflict are no longer relevant. But in reality world Zionism and Christian Imperialism, as well as world Communism, are conducting the fight against Islam and the Muslim community, first and foremost, on ideological grounds and with the sole aim of destroying this solid rock which, despite their concerted and sustained efforts, they have not been able to remove. The confrontation is not over control of territory or economic resources, or for military domination. If we believe that, we would play into our enemies' hands and would have no one but ourselves to blame for the consequences. "Never will the Jews, nor yet the Christians be pleased with you unless you follow their faith." (Verse 120) That is the heavy price that would have to be paid. They will accept nothing less. But God's instructions are very clear: "Say: 'God's guidance is the only true guidance.'" (Verse 120) The instruction is definite and emphatic: there is to be no negotiation or bargaining, no compromise or appeasement. The Prophet is warned that his wish to convey the message to those people and his eagerness for them to believe him, or his inclination to befriend them, should not distract him from the difficult but straight path he has taken: "Should you follow their desires after all the knowledge that has come to you, you would have none to protect you from God, nor to give you help." (Verse 120)" [1:123-124]

<p>Qur'ān 8:16</p> <p>Qur'ān 5:64</p>	<p>"For any one who turns his back on that day, except to fight or rally to his side, will bring the wrath of God on himself, and have Hell as abode; and what an evil destination!"</p> <p>"And We have caused enmity and hatred among them (which will last) till the Day of Resurrection. As often as they ignite the fires of war they are extinguished by God. Yet they rush around to spread corruption in the land; but God does not love those who are corrupt."</p>
<p>Hamas:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Leaving the circle of struggle with Zionism is high treason, and cursed be he who does that. "For any one who turns his back on that day, except to fight or rally to his side, will bring the wrath of God on himself, and have Hell as abode; and what an evil destination!". There is no way out except by concentrating all powers and energies to face this Nazi, vicious Tatar invasion. The alternative is loss of one's country, the dispersion of citizens, the spread of vice on earth and the destruction of religious values. Let every person know that he is responsible before Allah, for "the doer of the slightest good deed is rewarded in like, and the doer of the slightest evil deed is also rewarded in like." The Islamic Resistance Movement consider itself to be the spearhead of the circle of struggle with world Zionism and a step on the road. The Movement adds its efforts to the efforts of all those who are active in the Palestinian arena. Arab and Islamic Peoples should augment by further steps on their part; Islamic groupings all over the Arab world should also do the same, since all of these are the best-equipped for the future role in the fight with the warmongering Jews." [Art.32]
<p>al-Bayḍāwī:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "{For any one who turns his back on that day, except to fight} He intends turning after fleeing and misleading the enemy, thus it being a ruse of war. {or rally to his side} or rally to his other side from the Muslims nearby for him (i.e. the Messenger) to resort to." [1:379] • "{And We have caused enmity and hatred among them (which will last) till the Day of Resurrection} Thus they do not concur with their hearts and do not correspond with their statements. {As often as they ignite the fires of war they are extinguished by God} Whenever they desire war with the Messenger and provoke evil on him, God repulses them by bringing about a discontinuing conflict between them through their own evil, [...] they conflict with the ruling of the Torah God imposes Nebuchadnezzar II on them then they corrupt thus He imposes Futrus the Roman on them, then they corrupted and He imposes the Persians on them, then they corrupted again and He imposes the Muslims on them." [1:277]

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<p>Quṭb:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "These verses begin with a strong warning, a fearsome threat. Should the believers face their enemies who may in essence present themselves in a great show of power, they must not, under any circumstances, turn away, except for tactical reasons. These may include choosing a better position, carrying out a more effective plan, joining another group of believers, or moving to another Muslim stronghold in order to resume the fight. Deserters and people who turn away in flight deserve the most terrible double punishment of incurring God's wrath and being thrown into hell. Some scholars have expressed the view that this ruling applies only to the people of Badr, or to a battle in which the Prophet himself took part. But the overwhelming majority of scholars have emphasized its general application. They consider fleeing from battle as one of the gravest sins. [...] A believer should be firm and resolute, able to resist any force on earth, since he believes that God's power can overcome all powers. If a believer's heart experiences a tremor at a moment of danger, such a tremor should not go as far as making him flee from battle. The moment of anyone's death is determined by God alone. Hence, no believer may flee from battle fearing for his life. This should not constitute too much of a burden for anyone. A believer is a human being who encounters an enemy, who, in turn, is a human being. Hence, they are of the same nature. The believer, however, has the advantage of relying on the overpowering might of God Himself. Moreover, he is under God's care while he is alive, and he entrusts himself to God's care if he attains martyrdom." [7:81/85] • "Jewish groups continue to be hostile to one another, even though world Jewry may appear to be united at this period of time and capable of launching wars against Muslim countries and winning them. We must not, however, look at only a short period of time or cast only a partial view. Over 13 centuries, indeed since pre-Islamic days, the Jews have been hostile to one another, humiliated, and dispersed all over the globe. They will inevitably share the same fate, despite all the support they are receiving. The key to the whole matter is the existence of a true Islamic community, to whom God fulfills His promise. Where do we find today such a community which receives God's promise and becomes the means by which God accomplishes His purpose? When the Muslim nation returns to Islam, truly believes in it and conducts its whole life in accordance with Islamic law and constitution, God's warning to His most evil creatures will come true. The Jews know this and they use all their power and wicked scheming against the advocates of Islamic revival throughout the world. They level at them, through their puppets and stooges, brutal blows in total disregard of all laws and values. God, will, however, accomplish His will. [4:147-148]

